

MANUFACTURING OF A THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL AIRCRAFT COMPONENT

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ABSTRACT: Delft Aerospace Engineering was highly involved in the design and certification of the Eaglet, a 2 seat all composite aircraft produced by Euro-Enaer. The Eaglet prototype will serve as a flying test bed for several development projects of the university. The first project will be the re-design and manufacturing of the rudder in thermoplastic composites. The material will be Cetex[®] produced by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, either carbon or glass reinforced PEI. Rubber- and diaphragm forming, folding and resistance welding are the production techniques to be used for manufacturing the rudder. The design and manufacturing process will be performed in cooperation with the Dutch Airworthiness Authority, in order to certify the rudder according to JAR/FAR 23, utility category.

Key words: Thermoplastic composites, folding, rubber forming, welding, structural component

INTRODUCTION

The research on thermoplastic composites at the Faculty of Aerospace Engineering of the Delft University of Technology is focussed on the design and manufacturing of large primary aircraft structures. The increasing size of aircraft, as is illustrated by the development of the Airbus A380 (550-800 seat aircraft), forces the aeronautic industry to extend the limits of technology in order to be able to design and produce such aircraft. The state-of-the-art in aircraft design is the design and manufacture of primary structures in metal or thermoset composites. During the last 10 years new composites have been developed based on thermoplastic matrices. These thermoplastic composites offer, compared with metals, significant weight reduction at no cost penalty, preservation of environment, preservation of natural resources/energy and improvement of work environment. Compared with thermoset composites these materials offer a reduction of manufacturing cost, preservation of environment and of natural resources/energy and improvement of work environment. The use of thermoplastic composites is currently, though growing, limited to non-structural interior parts like stow bins and to small secondary structures like ribs for flaps. Also more complex welded structures like the fixed leading edge of the A340-600 have been developed but primary structures have not been developed so far. The incentive of this research project is to design and manufacture a structural component for a General Aviation aircraft. The design and manufacturing process will be certified according to JAR23. The project can be regarded as a technology demonstrator for thermoplastic composites and as a first step towards the design and manufacturing of a large structural aircraft component.

EURO-ENAER EAGLET

Figure 1: Euro-Enaer Eaglet

The Eaglet is 2-Seat aircraft (Fig.1) that has been produced by Euro-Enaer, The Netherlands. The airplane has limited aerobatics capabilities, and is designed for pilot training, leisure and surveillance. It has a full composite structure and is certified according to JAR/FAR 23, utility category.

The Faculty of Aerospace Engineering of the Delft University of Technology was highly involved in the technical design and prototyping process as well as on aerodynamical design and wind tunnel testing [ref.1-2]. The faculty recently bought the prototype of the Eaglet, which will serve as a flying test bed for a full-scale validation/realization of several research projects.

It was chosen to re-design the rudder of the Eaglet in thermoplastic composites. The reason for this choice was:

1. The rudder is a primary aircraft structure.
2. The rudder is very much similar to the other components of the family of "movables" (flaps, ailerons, etc.)
3. The thermoplastic composite rudder can be installed without chances in the fuselage/tail design.
4. A similar project has been performed on Vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding [ref.3].
5. The manufacturing of the rudder incorporates the main thermoplastic composite processing techniques: welding, folding, diaphragm- and rubber forming.

The current Eaglet rudder is made of glass/epoxy and PMI foam and built up from 8 components: two shells, four ribs, one spar and a leading edge. The shells and the leading edge are individually produced; the ribs and spar are cut from prefabricated sandwich plates, the sandwich shells and the leading edge are moulded parts. All components are made with wet lay-up followed by vacuum bagging and oven cure. The components are assembled using wet hand lay-up and bonding with thickened resin. The rudder surface is finished with filler, to obtain an aerodynamically smooth surface, and paint. The total weight of the rudder is 5.7 kg, including balance weight and hinges. The Eaglet rudder is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Eaglet rudder

RE-DESIGN OF THE EAGLET RUDDER

The current glass/epoxy sandwich design will be re-designed into a full thermoplastic composite monolithic structure. At this moment the only continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic

composites being certified for aeronautical applications are APC-2[®] (carbon fibre/PEEK) of Victrex and Cetex[®] of Ten Cate Advanced Composites. Only Cetex[®] will be used in this project because of the lower costs, good deformability and their wide spread application in aircraft components. Two grades of Cetex[®] are available, either with a PPS or a PEI matrix and reinforced with carbon or glass fibres. In the first phase of the project carbon/PEI will be used for the whole structure while in the second phase carbon/PPS will be used. From structural point of view carbon fibres are not required, however, they are being used since this rudder serves as a demonstrator for the design/manufacturing of larger, thus heavier loaded, movables.

Figure 3: Eaglet rudder re-design basis

The positions of the hinges will remain the same as for the original rudder where these hinges are supported by ribs. The position of these hinge ribs is fixed. The bare structure from which the design starts can be seen in Fig. 3, in the design process, elements will be added to ensure the strength and stiffness of the rudder.

Loads on the rudder

Figure 4: triangular wing box

The triangular wing box carries the loads on the rudder, as can be seen in Figure 4. In the stress and deformation calculations only this part of the rudder will be considered. The loads as determined by Euro-ENAEER during the original design process will be used, since the geometry and flight conditions of the rudder will not change [ref.4]. The load is a pressure distribution perpendicular to the skin. In case of the old design this was not a problem, since the skin was a sandwich construction, which provided sufficient in-plane stiffness. However, the new design will have thin skins, therefore, some

stiffening, in the form of stiffeners and/or ribs, is necessary. These stiffening elements have to limit the deformation of the rudder to an acceptable level. The most important deflection is the deflection of the skin panel, since this will influence the airflow and, subsequently, the flight performance of the aircraft. For the maximum deformation of the skin panel a deflection of 10 mm was assumed acceptable. Another reason for stiffening the

- 2. Resistance wire bare and in
- 4. Ribs
- 4.2. First hinge rib
- 4.3. Second hinge rib
- 4.4. Second rib in-between hinges
- 4.5. Third hinge rib
- 4.6. Top cap support rib
- 4.7. Horn close rib
- 5. Leading edge (could be build up from 3 parts)
- 6. Bottom cap
- 7. Upper cap
- 8. Horn skin 1
- 9. Horn skin 2

Figure 8: Rudder elements, hinges are not included in the exploded view

Figure 11: Spar-skin connection

Figure 5: Example of ICAD to Patran export

